

STRUGGLE AGAINST SPIRITUAL THREATS AFFECTING SOCIETY IN THE PROCESS OF GLOBALIZATION

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In the 21st century, humanity took a new step towards a new civilizational development. Unprecedented changes in scientific and technical spheres marked a new way of development of society in a revolutionary way. In this personality relationship, he lived in contact with difficult and resistant conditions. This rapidly changing era is going to mark new and new directions of human development. The peculiarity of this historical period is that, first of all, it is being realized in the democratization of the principles of socio-political relations of the society towards humanism. The content, scope, and character of the traditionally stereotyped concepts in various spheres of social and political life are changing. We can see this in the globalization, universalization and integration of social, economic, political, and spiritual processes on a global scale.

If we take a deeper look at world affairs, then the differentiation of all its branches, the adaptation and change of ideas and ideologies according to the ideas of a similar group of related people are taking place. At the beginning of the 21st century, these dynamic processes are influenced by views, theories, and concepts. Traditional ideas and ideologies that exist in the world, in one way or another, are undergoing the process of adapting to the times. On the other hand, they are richer than new paradigms and rules. We can see these in the example of liberalism, conservatism, social-democratic ideologies. National ideologies, which are the youngest ideologies of our time, are also popular. One of the situations that should be mentioned separately is that there are destructive ideas and ideologies at the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century, and it is necessary to fight against such destructive ideas. Because our time has a false ideological appearance. Analyzing it, learning from all the constructive ideas and ideologies in the world, and fighting against destructive ideas are among the most important tasks. A mechanism of struggle against destructive ideologies has been developed for the progressive development of our country. The goals and tasks to be implemented in this long-term strategic plan were noted. In particular, the fifth direction of the action strategy will be of particular importance in the fight against such threats.

If we look at the ideological picture of the present time, we can see various ideologies that have contributed to the progress of humanity, namely, liberalism and neoliberalism, conservatism and neoconservatism, social democracy,

national ideologies that have produced positive results in society and continue to do so. Understanding the meaning and content of these ideological concepts, the drivers of their development, is one of the current scientific tasks.

In order to achieve the great goals set for itself, every state and society must have a theoretically defined, clear and clearly defined idea and ideology, be guided by them, and based on them, determine its internal and external policy, economic, social, and spiritual enlightenment responsibilities. In order to ensure the bright future of the society and the state, there is a need for a fully developed ideology. The great Chinese philosopher Confucius spoke about the necessity of ideology to organize the state.

As our President Sh.M. Mirziyoev mentioned, we need to set clear goals in the way of impartial treatment. In this way, he expresses his opinion that we should be critical, think clearly and create new innovative ideas. Our respected head of state said that sitting in awe of the achieved achievements is considered the biggest obstacle on the way to development.

It is no secret to anyone that the biggest threat to the development of society is the ideological threat. That is why the struggle against ideological threats is noted as the main task of every state. The attention of the media is bringing out the invisible but very scary ideological wars between the countries. As a solution to ideological wars, we need to mold ideological knowledge, that is, immunity. If ideological knowledge, that is, immunity, is not well suited, an ideological void has appeared in a person. Processes of showing political, religious and other ideological influences are taking place in the world. These can be shown as an example of a winning culture that has a quick impact on everyday life. Apart from this, we can increase the political influence in our daily life. We can cite axiological and praxeological approaches as a way to prevent and fight against such effects.

In general, in creating an ideological atmosphere, educating the masses and offering a good marriage paradigm is the first condition. Noting the progressive development of our country in such historical processes, our President Sh.M. Mirziyoev said, "Today we are going to go on the path of innovative development aimed at fundamentally renewing all aspects of the state and society. Because in today's fast-paced world, who wins? "New ideas, new ideas, and new reforms will be implemented in every field of opinion that a state based on innovation will win".

References:

1. Ш.М.Мирзиёев. «Янги Ўзбекистон стратегияси». – Тошкент: «O'zbekiston» нашриёти, 2021 йил.

2. Жаҳон фалсафаси тарихидан лавҳалар (тажрибавий матн) I китоб. Тошкент - 2004 йил.
3. Biyimbetov J.K. Information Society Development Trends: Philosophical Analysis of Basic Concepts // Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – America: 2021. // ISSN 2770-0003. SJIF Impact Factor (2022): 5.909. –Б. 74-77.
4. Biyimbetov J.K. Political, economic, cultural and information development of the world in the process of globalization // Science and education in Karakalpakstan. Karakalpak State University name after Berdakh –Нукус: 2021. ISSN 2181-9203. –P.91-92. (09.00.00; № 20).
5. Biyimbetov J.K. Philosophical analysis of the problem of information psychological security // Адам элeмi (Философский и общественно-гуманитарный журнал). –Kazakstan: 2021. ISSN №1999-5849. –Б. 3-9. (09.00.00; № 09).
6. Бийимбетов Ж.К. Қәуипсизликти тәмийнлеу мәселелериниң жәмийет турмысындағы әҳмийети // Бердақ номидаги Қорақалпоқ давлат университетининг Ахборотномаси. –Нукус: ҚДУ, 2020. ISSN 2010-9075. –Б. 174-175. (09.00.00; № 10).
7. Biyimbetov J.K. Problems of protection against threats affecting human consciousness in the processes of information civilization // 8th-International Conference on Research in Humanities, Applied Sciences and Education. Germany.: – Berlin: 2022. –P. 1-3.
8. Biyimbetov J.K. Philosophical characteristics of information security and analysis of human problems in the 21st century // International Conference on Developments in Education. Netherlands.: – Amsterdam: 2022. –P. 1-3.
9. Biyimbetov J.K. Socio-philosophical aspects of political culture formation in the process of globalization // Palarch's journal of archaeology of egypt. – Egypt: 2020. ISSN: 1567-214X. –P. 100-109.
10. Мамбеткаримов Р.Р. Factors for Forming Critical Thinking in Students in the Educational Process // Research Journal of Humanities and Cultural Studies. 29-may 2022. Amerika. ISSN 2770-0003. SJIF Impact Factor (2022): 5.909. –Б. 1.
11. Мамбеткаримов Р.Р. Basic Principles and Methods of Using Media Education for forming Students' Analytical Thinking // Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities. 15-noyabr. 2021.Amerika. ISSN 2769-996X. SJIF Impact Factor (2021): 5.818. –Б. 63-68.
12. Mambetkarimov R.R. The problem of analytical thinking in the current modern education system // International Multidisciplinary Conference. England.: – Manchester: 2022. –P. 128-131.

13. Mambetkarimov R.R. The relationship between the development of analytical thinking and problem-based learning in quality education // 8th-International Conference on Research in Humanities, Applied Sciences and Education., Germany.: – Berlin: 2022. –P. 77-81.
14. Tlepbergenova Perizat. Ecology of the Bukhara Deer in Our Country (Distribution and Origin). Research Journal of Applied Medical Sciences. 25.04.2022. 16-бет.
15. Tlepbergenova Perizat. Prospects For the Development of Ecological Tourism in Uzbekistan. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. 2021-йил 15-ноябрь. 144-бет.
16. Tlepbergenova Perizat. Global ecological problems: Essence and possible solutions. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR). 2021-йил 5-май. 108-бет.
17. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Matritsa rangi. Matritsa rangini tuzatish usullari. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 280-291. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1758> dan olindi.
18. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Matritsalar va ular ustida amallar. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 226-238. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1752> dan olindi.
19. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Vektorlar. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 173-182. <https://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1747> dan olindi.
20. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar tizimini echishning matritsa, Gauss va Gauss-Jordan usullari. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 312-322. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1761> dan olindi.
21. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Chiziqli operatorlar va komissiya xossalari. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 133-145. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1744> dan olindi.
22. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Chiziqli operatorlar va komissiya xossalari. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 146-152. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1744> dan olindi.
23. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Kvadratik forma va uni kanonik korinishga keltirish. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 153-172. <https://www.openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1746> dan olindi.
24. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Arifmetik vektor fazo va unga misollar. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 109-120. <https://www.openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1742> dan olindi.

25. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Vektorlarning skalyar ko'paytmasi. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 183-191. <https://www.openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1748> dan olindi.
26. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Vektorlarning vektor va aralash ko'paytmalari. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 271-279. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1757> dan olindi.
27. Usmonov, M.T. & Shokirov, Sh.H, (2022). Teylor formulasini matematik masalalarni echishdagi ahamiyati. "«Science and Education» Scientific Journal" Scientific Journal, Tom-3, 19-23.
28. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Compatibility, Actions on Compatibility. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR), Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 10-13.
29. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Number. The Establishment of the Concept of Natural Number and Zero. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJASIR), Vol. 4 Issue 12, December - 2020, Pages: 7-9.
30. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Compatibility, Actions on Compatibility. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS), Vol. 4 Issue 12, December - 2020, Pages: 66-68.
31. Usmonov M. T. General Concept of Mathematics and Its History. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR). Vol. 4 Issue 12, December - 2020, Pages: 38-42
32. Usmonov M. T. Asymmetric Cryptosystems. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 6-9.
33. Usmonov M. T. Basic Concepts of Information Security. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 5-8.
34. Usmonov M. T. Communication Control Systems, Methodology. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 47-50.
35. Usmonov M. T. Compatibility between the Two Package Elements. Binar Relations and Their Properties. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 52-54.
36. Usmonov M. T. Cryptographic Protection of Information. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 24-26.

37. Usmonov M. T. Electronic Digital Signature. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 30-34.
38. Usmonov M. T. "Equal" And "Small" Relations. Add. Laws Of Addition. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAIRS) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 27-29.
39. Usmonov M. T. Establish Network Protection. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 14-21.
40. Usmonov M. T. Fundamentals of Symmetric Cryptosystem. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
41. Usmonov M. T. General Concepts of Mathematics. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAIRS) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 14-16.
42. Usmonov M. T. Identification and Authentication. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 39-47.
43. Usmonov M. T. Information Protection and Its Types. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 1-4.
44. Usmonov M. T. Information Protection in Wireless Communication Systems. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 61-64.
45. Usmonov M. T. Information protection supply. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 12-15.
46. Usmonov M. T. Information Security Policy. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 70-73.
47. Usmonov M. T. Information War. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 79-82.
48. Usmonov M. T. International and National Legal Base in the Field Of Information Security. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 7-14.

49. Usmonov M. T. Legal Legislative Basis for Detection of Information Crime. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 80-87.

